

Additional Records for the Gerromorpha and Nepomorpha (Hemiptera: Heteroptera) Fauna of Turkey

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ABSTRACT: This study was performed in the period March-September in the years 2013 and 2014 in various freshwater habitats in Edirne of Thrace region in order to determine the aquatic and semi-aquatic Heteroptera fauna of the city. As a result 28 species belonging to 14 families from Gerromorpha and Nepomorpha were identified. Habitat and distribution informations of the species were given.

KEYWORDS: Additional records, Gerromorpha, Nepomorpha, fauna, Turkey

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INTRODUCTION

Gerromorpha and Nepomorpha infraorders are two of the 7 infraorders subject to the Heteroptera (Hemiptera) suborder and include aquatic and semiaquatic species. In the Palearctic Region, Gerromorpha and Nepomorpha are represented by 92 genera, 582 species and 39 subspecies belonging to 16 families, while 78 species / subspecies (51 species / 25 subspecies) belonging to 14 families are known in our country (Fent *et al.* 2011; Aukema *et al.*, 2013, Banbal & Fent, 2016).

The first comprehensive study on Gerromorpha and Nepomorpha in Turkey dates back to Hoberlandt (1952) in which he

summarized all the available records from the country. Recently Fent *et al.* (2011), performed a detailed study in which a critical checklist was given for aquatic and semi-aquatic Heteroptera of Turkey and Thrace Region based on both new (4 new records for Turkey fauna and 4 new records for Thrace Region fauna) and all previous records. After this study, Dursun (2012), Topkara (2013), Topkara *et al.* (2013), Banbal & Fent (2016), Fent & Dursun (2018), Dursun & Fent (2018, 2019) have conducted studies in various regions and Banbal & Fent (2016) Turkey addition of a new record for the number of known species of fauna has increased to 77.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The research material was collected from various natural and artificial aquatic wetlands, includes natural and artificial lakes, such as lakes, ponds, dams, rivers, streams irrigation channels and trough, in 129 locations determined in Edirne Province during the March- September periods between 2013 and 2014, especially in the spring-summer periods when Gerromorpha and Nepomorpha species are active.

The material was sampled from the water body, water surface and waterfront with the help of a sweeping net and all the

sampled material was placed and kept in 96% ethanol containing tubes. Male genital organs were dissected and parameres were used in the identification of the species. The diagnostic keys of Nieser (1972), Poisson (1957), Jansson (1986), Andersen (1990, 1993), Rabitsch (2005) and Kanyukova (2006) were consulted in identifications of the sampled material.

The researched localities in Edirne province are shown on the map (Fig.1) and names coordinates, altitudes, habitat features of localities, and dates of field studies are given in Table 1.

Figure 1. Collecting localities in Edirne province.

Table 1. Localities, coordinates, altitudes, habitats and research dates in Edirne Province

Locality No	Locality	Coordinates	Altitude (m)	Habitat	Collection Dates
1	Edirne- Merkez	41°40'37.67"K 26°33'20.57"D	41m	Stream Stream Meriç River Stream Roadside Stream	10.06.2013 21.06.2013 23.07.2013 03.08.2013 08.09.2013 19.09.2014
2	Süloğlu- Büyükgerdelli	41°45'6.69"K 26°55'54.45"D	163m	Pond pool Stream Puddle	12.06.2013 15.06.2013 17.06.2013 13.03.2014
3	Enez- Hisarlı	40°43'14.50"K 26°12'40.56"D	203m	Pond	23.06.2013 04.09.2013
4	Merkez-Pazarkule	41°39'41.85"K 26°29'44.79"D	35m	Meriç River	23.07.2013
5	Lalapaşa- Çömlekköy	41°50'32.35"K 26°36'31.68"D	94m	Çoban Stream	14.08.2013
6	Merkez- Avarız	41°44'49.80"K 26°32'39.63"D	42m	Tunca River	14.08.2013
7	Havsa- Söğütüdere	41°38'8.98"K 26°48'14.94"D	112m	Seymen Stream	20.08.2013
8	Merkez- İskender	41°37'47.26"K 26°40'22.72"D	87m	Sazlı Stream	20.08.2013 15.03.2014
9	Merkez- Ahi	41°46'35.86"K 26°24'22.00"D	87m	Stream	22.08.2013
10	Merkez- Uzgaç	41°47'32.17"K 26°26'16.25"D	163m	Stream	22.08.2013
11	Uzunköprü	41°16'16.53"K 26°41'58.99"D	32m	Ergene River	30.08.2013
12	Between Uzunköprü- Bayramlı- Yeniköy	41°19'24.19"K 26°47'44.32"D	80m	Rice field Water channel	30.08.2013
13	Uzunköprü- Bildır	41°17'15.89"K 26°53'33.02"D	80m	Stream Pond	30.08.2013
14	Uzunköprü- Çöpköy	41°13'30.44"K 26°49'24.23"D	87m	Stream Pond	30.08.2013
15	Uzunköprü- Danişment	41°18'15.11"K 26°54'4.82"D	60m	Koca Stream	30.08.2013
16	Uzunköprü- Turnacı	41°15'5.69"K 26°55'29.61"D	90m	Stream	30.08.2013
17	Süloğlu	41°46'10.30"K 26°54'30.92"D	156m	Stream	31.08.2013
18	Lalapaşa	41°50'26.21"K 26°44'11.25"D	166m	Pond	01.09.2013
19	Lalapaşa- Hacıdanişment	41°54'33.12"K 26°49'23.88"D	438m	Trough	01.09.2013
20	Lalapaşa- Süleymandanişment	41°53'49.92"K 26°53'25.58"D	384m	Pond	01.09.2013
21	Lalapaşa- Ömeroba	41°55'24.52"K 26°55'50.21"D	350m	Süloğlu Stream	01.09.2013
22	Süloğlu- Geçinli	41°43'51.49"K 26°50'53.55"D	151m	Stream	01.09.2013
23	Between Süloğlu- Lalapaşa	41°48'12.16"K 26°50'49.45"D	160m	Pond	01.09.2013
24	İpsala- Koyuntepe- Telmata	40°46'4.76"K 26°20'33.15"D	28m	Lake	03.09.2013
25	Between Keşan- Kılıçköy- Karahisar	40°46'25.89"K 26°31'53.33"D	16m	Water channel Stream	03.09.2013

Table 1. Continued...

29	Enez- Gülçavuş	40°37'18.50"K 26°10'11.69"D	18m	Trough	04.09.2013
30	Enez- Sultanıçe	40°37'16.02"K 26° 9'13.38"D	36m	Stream	04.09.2013
31	Uzunköprü- Alıç	41° 3'36.95"K 26°39'3.29"D	114m	Alıç Stream	06.09.2013
32	Uzunköprü- Altınyazı	41° 4'18.00"K 26°34'32.00"D	24m	irrigation channel	06.09.2013
33	Uzunköprü- Değirmen- ci	41°18'47.11"K 26°41'53.07"D	49m	Stream Pond	06.09.2013
34	Uzunköprü- Hamidiye	41° 9'9.84"K 26°39'56.35"D	108m	Stream	06.09.2013
35	Uzunköprü- Kadiğılı	41° 3'28.23"K 26°41'8.31"D	139m	Fountain	06.09.2013
36	Uzunköprü- Kavacık	41°11'8.13"K 26°40'12.27"D	52m	Pond Trough	06.09.2013
37	Uzunköprü- Kırkavak	41°12'31.28"K 26°45'0.91"D	80m	Stream	06.09.2013
38	Uzunköprü- Türkobası	41° 5'40.95"K 26°36'24.09"D	26m	Ana Stream	06.09.2013
39	Keşan	40°51'44.40"K 26°37'54.88"D	96m	Koca Stream dam evacuation	09.09.2013
40	Keşan- Büyükdoğanca	40°46'24.60"K 26°34'59.52"D	30m	Söğütlük Stream	09.09.2013
41	Keşan- Çeltik	40°40'59.90"K 26°33'23.62"D	140m	Stream	09.09.2013
42	Keşan- Dişbudak	40°43'17.23"K 26°34'27.32"D	92m	Stream	09.09.2013
43	Keşan- Doğanca	40°51'44.39"K 26°37'54.88"D	92m	Stream	09.09.2013
44	Keşan- Mecidiye	40°38'31.31"K 26°32'30.54"D	45m	Stream	09.09.2013 26.08.2014
45	Keşan- Mercan	40°44'49.93"K 26°36'13.47"D	38m	Dam evacuation irrigation channel	09.09.2013
46	Keşan- Sazlıdere	40°39'38.22"K 26°41'10.63"D	119m	Stream Trough	09.09.2013
47	Keşan- Yerlisu	40°43'30.59"K 26°43'49.77"D	174m	Water channel	09.09.2013
48	Enez- Abdurrahim	40°38'25.91"K 26°15'30.65"D	27m	Stream Trough	12.09.2013
49	Enez- Karaincirli	40°37'38.11"K 26°17'54.14"D	32m	Suvat Stream	12.09.2013
50	Enez-Vakıf	40°36'58.41"K 26°15'28.12"D	28m	Stream	12.09.2013
51	Enez- Yenimahalle	40°48'55.84"K 26°12'38.34"D	30m	Pond	12.09.2013
52	İpsala	40°55'17.00"K 26°22'60.00"D	20m	Stream DSİ-Water channel	12.09.2013
53	İpsala- Balabancık	41° 2'4.57"K 26°24'11.37"D	36m	Stream Trough	12.09.2013
54	İpsala- Sultanköy	40°59'49.03"K 26°25'57.80"D	59m	Dam evacuation Trough	12.09.2013
55	İpsala- Teflikiye	41° 3'49.55"K 26°29'40.64"D	11m	irrigation channel	12.09.2013
56	İpsala- Yenikarpuzlu	40°49'58.34"K 26°17'38.21"D	20m	Pond Water channel	12.09.2013
57	Meriç	41°11'32.04"K 26°25'15.11"D	40m	Koca Stream	12.09.2013
58	Meriç- Akçadam	41°18'26.52"K 26°31'58.67"D	60m	Trough	12.09.2013
59	Meriç- Hasırcıarnavut	41°16'24.77"K 26°27'39.82"D	54m	Pond	12.09.2013
60	Meriç- Karayusuflu	41°15'49.94"K 26°25'59.04"D	24m	Pond	12.09.2013
61	Meriç- Seren	41°18'50.72"K 26°30'54.98"D	40m	Pond	12.09.2013
62	Meriç- Yenicegörece	41° 7'51.67"K 26°28'3.80"D	20m	Trough	12.09.2013

Table 1. Continued...

63	Uzunköprü-Çalıköy	41°17'20.19"K 26°35'52.23"D	97m	Pond	12.09.2013
64	Enez-Yenimahalle	40°47'12.50"K 26°12'4.09"D	19m	Water channel	12.09.2013
65	Merkez- Budakdoğanca	41°45'39.14"K 26°20'31.88"D	116m	Pond	15.09.2013
66	Merkez- Ekmekçi	41°44'19.86"K 26°27'54.30"D	147m	Stream	15.09.2013
67	Merkez- Eskikadın	41°42'24.74"K 26°27'25.97"D	74m	Pond	15.09.2013
68	Merkez- Karabulut	41°46'7.01"K 26°26'18.85"D	123m	Trough	15.09.2013
69	Merkez- Kemal	41°44'7.82"K 26°23'41.11"D	84m	Stream Trough	15.09.2013
70	Lalapaşa- Sarıdanışment	41°51'58.12"K 26°49'44.71"D	285m	Stream	21.09.2013
71	Lalapaşa- Taşlımüsellim	41°49'23.38"K 26°46'6.53"D	180m	Stream	21.09.2013
72	Süloğlu- Domurcalı	41°48'57.48"K 26°49'6.68"D	199m	Trough	21.09.2013
73	Süloğlu- Sülecik	41°48'50.68"K 26°50'59.27"D	208m	Stream	21.09.2013
74	Süloğlu- Tatarlar	41°50'8.00"K 26°53'8.24"D	236m	Trough	21.09.2013
75	Süloğlu- Yağcılı	41°47'6.48"K 26°49'41.44"D	165m	Stream	21.09.2013
76	Merkez- Demirhanlı	41°41'49.39"K 26°44'13.26"D	114m	Stream	07.03.2014
77	Merkez- Hacıumur	41°43'7.93"K 26°47'16.13"D	136m	Trough Pond	07.03.2014 13.03.2014
78	Merkez- Musabeyli	41°41'52.73"K 26°39'44.33"D	113m	pool	07.03.2014
79	Between Merkez- Musabeyli- Demirhanlı	41°41'44.16"K 26°41'43.72"D	113m	Pond	07.03.2014
80	Between Süloğlu- Küküler	41°44'43.92"K 26°55'4.96"D	160m	Pond	13.03.2014
81	Havsa- Arpaç	41°41'30.48"K 26°52'56.76"D	119m	Stream	15.03.2014
82	Havsa- Azatlı	41°30'3.11"K 26°41'56.12"D	100m	Trough	29.05.2014
83	Merkez- Bosnaköy	41°37'20.67"K 26°33'2.39"D	33m	Rice field	29.05.2014
84	Merkez- Üyükütatar	41°32'39.19"K 26°36'45.32"D	44m	Stream Water channel	29.05.2014
85	Merkez- Hasanağa	41°43'29.45"K 26°37'27.77"D	60m	Stream	01.06.2014
86	Meriç- Kavaklı	41°13'59.08"K 26°31'16.21"D	77m	Stream Trough	01.06.2014 04.08.2014
87	Merkez- Korucu	41°47'30.19"K 26°39'13.38"D	140m	Pond	01.06.2014
88	Havsa- Çukurköy	41°28'1.53"K 26°49'7.96"D	60m	Stream	03.06.2014
89	Havsa- Şerbettar	41°27'44.45"K 26°45'32.37"D	83m	Ova Stream	03.06.2014
90	Havsa- Bostanlı	41°36'38.00"K 26°58'8.59"D	88m	Stream	11.06.2014
91	Havsa- Osmanlı	41°35'11.85"K 26°50'15.55"D	91m	Stream Trough	11.06.2014
92	Havsa- Yolageldi	41°31'0.69"K 26°56'52.01"D	54m	Trough	11.06.2014
93	Süloğlu- Kerametlin	41°47'12.68"K 26°58'35.10"D	200m	Pond	12.06.2014
94	Havsa- Tahal	41°25'38.18"K 26°51'12.11"D	50m	Stream	13.06.2014
95	Süloğlu- Çeşmeköy arası	41°45'26.53"K 27° 0'52.20"D	200m	Trough	13.06.2014
96	Uzunköprü- Eskiköy	41°19'47.28"K 26°38'42.72"D	72m	Puddle	13.06.2014
97	Uzunköprü- Meşeli	41°23'19.95"K 26°43'30.96"D	88m	Stream	13.06.2014

Table 1. Continued...

98	Uzunköprü- Saçlımüsellim	41°25'21.03"K 26°37'54.33"D	28m	Trough	13.06.2014
99	Lalapaşa- Çalidere	41°56'20.31"K 26°44'40.20"D	230m	Stream	15.07.2014
100	Lalapaşa- Hamzabeyli	41°57'50.30"K 26°38'33.77"D	378m	Pond	15.07.2014
101	Lalapaşa- Kalkansögüt	41°58'14.78"K 26°48'45.79"D	415m	Stream	15.07.2014
102	Lalapaşa- Vaysal	41°56'28.76"K 26°52'12.22"D	438m	Pond	15.07.2014
103	Meriç- Nasuhbey	41°12'54.22"K 26°20'49.50"D	33m	Pond	04.08.2014
104	Meriç- Olacak	41°13'1.55"K 26°28'25.64"D	60m	Pond	04.08.2014
105	Uzunköprü- Çiftlikköy	41°14'52.83"K 26°37'17.15"D	12m	Stream	04.08.2014
106	İpsala- İbriktepe	41° 0'42.00"K 26°30'10.00"D	127m	Stream	12.08.2014
107	İpsala- Sarıcaali	40°59'8.10"K 26°22'57.00"D	23m	Stream	12.08.2014
108	Meriç- Adasarhanlı	41° 4'59.10"K 26°21'32.00"D	38m	Pond	12.08.2014
109	Meriç- Büyükaltağaç	41° 6'46.17"K 26°24'25.27"D	40m	Stream	12.08.2014
110	Meriç- Subaşı	41° 8'34.27"K 26°22'25.17"D	19m	Pond	12.08.2014
111	Uzunköprü- Balaban	41° 5'25.99"K 26°32'51.77"D	26m	Trough	12.08.2014
112	İpsala- Korucu	41°47'30.19"K 26°39'13.38"D	75m	Stream	23.08.2014
113	İpsala- Turpçular	40°56'30.93"K 26°26'8.22"D	29m	Stream	23.08.2014
114	Keşan- Beğendik	40°55'38.15"K 26°34'16.66"D	114m	Pond	23.08.2014
115	Keşan- Çobançeşme	40°57'42.91"K 26°40'6.94"D	171m	Dam evacuation	23.08.2014
116	Keşan- Kozköy	41° 1'16.62"K 26°36'42.90"D	64m	Stream	23.08.2014
117	Keşan- Lalacık	40°58'15.72"K 26°36'13.09"D	158m	Trough	23.08.2014
118	Enez- Işıklı	40°43'8.04"K 26°18'35.29"D	27m	Stream	24.08.2014
119	Enez- Yenice	40°41'43.17"K 26° 9'10.32"D	70m	Trough	24.08.2014
120	Keşan- Boztepe	40°50'30.25"K 26°31'12.86"D	48m	Trough	26.08.2014
121	Keşan- Pınar	40°42'26.22"K 26°38'16.92"D	174m	Water channel	26.08.2014
122	Keşan- Yaylaköy	40°37'46.33"K 26°23'29.09"D	154m	Puddle	26.08.2014
123	Havsa- Abalar	41°32'31.70"K 26°44'38.04"D	70m	Stream	30.08.2014
124	Havsa- Oğulpaşa	41°36'1.68"K 26°44'52.34"D	85m	Stream	30.08.2014
125	Uzunköprü- Beykonağı	41°10'21.46"K 26°47'32.52"D	115m	Stream	31.08.2014
126	Uzunköprü- Dereköy	41° 9'31.87"K 26°42'24.90"D	57m	Stream	31.08.2014
127	Uzunköprü- Elmalı	41°10'43.41"K 26°53'22.19"D	120m	Trough	31.08.2014
128	Uzunköprü- Harmanlı	41° 6'2.56"K 26°44'54.35"D	180m	Trough	31.08.2014
129	Uzunköprü- Süleymaniye	41° 7'14.49"K 26°48'18.65"D	281m	Trough	31.08.2014

RESULTS**GERROMORPHA Popov, 1971****GERRIDAE Leach, 1815*****Aquarius Schellenberg, 1800******Aquarius paludum paludum*
(Fabricius, 1794)**

Material examined: Havsa- Şerbettar (83m)- Ova Stream: 03.06.2014, 1♂; İpsala- Turpçular (29m)- Stream: 23.08.2014, 4♀♀, 4♂♂; Keşan- Dişbudak (92m)- Stream: 09.09.2013, 1♀; Mercan (38m)- Dam evacuation: 09.09.2013, 5♂♂; Pınar (174m)- Water channel: 26.08.2014, 3♀♀, 2♂♂; Lalapaşa- Hamzabeyli (378m)- Pond: 15.07.2014, 1♀; Ömeroba (350m)- Süloğlu Stream: 01.09.2013, 4♀♀, 2♂♂; Vaysal (438m)- Pond: 15.07.2014, 1♀, 1♂; Meriç- Büyükaltağaç (40m)- Stream: 12.08.2014, 1♂; Hasırcıarnavut (54m)- Pond: 12.09.2013, 5♀♀, 9♂♂; Karayusuflu (24m)- Pond: 12.09.2013, 5♂♂; Koca Stream (40m)-: 12.09.2013, 1♀, 2♂♂; Nasuhbey (33m)- Pond: 04.08.2014, 1♂; Subaşı (19m)- Pond: 12.08.2014, 8♀♀, 1♂; Merkez- Avarız (42m) - Tunca River: 14.08.2013, 3♀♀; Budakdoğanca (116m)- Pond: 15.09.2013, 2♂♂; Bosnaköy (33m) - Rice field: 29.05.2014, 3♂♂; Eskikadın (74m)- Pond: 15.09.2013, 1♂; Hasanağa (60m)- Stream: 01.06.2014, 1♀, 1♂; İskender (87m) - Sazlı Stream: 20.08.2013, 3♀♀, 4♂♂; Kent Ormanı (41m) - Meriç River: 23.07.2013, 1♀; Orhaniye (15m) - Stream: 03.09.2013, 1♀; Merkez-Pazarkule (35m)- Meriç River: 23.07.2013, 2♀♀, 2♂♂; Süloğlu- Büyükgerdelli (163m)- Stream: 17.06.2013, 2♀♀; Stream (156m): 31.08.2013, 6♀♀, 3♂♂; Sülecik (208m)- Stream: 21.09.2013, 1♀, 2♂♂; Yağcılı (165)- Stream: 21.09.2013, 3♂♂; Uzunköprü- Alıç (114m)- Alıç Stream: 06.09.2013, 1♀, 3♂♂; Altınyazı (24m)- irrigation channel: 06.09.2013, 1♀; Bildir (80m) - Pond: 30.08.2013, 2♀♀, 6♂♂; Çalıköy (97m)- Pond: 12.09.2013, 2♂♂; Çöpköy (87m) - Pond: 30.08.2013, 3♂♂; Dereköy (57m)- Stream: 31.08.2014, 1♀, 1♂;

(108m)- Stream: 06.09.2013, 1♀.

***Aquarius ventralis* (Fieber, 1860)**

Material examined: Havsa- Arpaç (119m)- Stream: 15.03.2014, 3♀♀, 7♂♂; Bostanlı (88m)- Stream: 11.06.2014, 8♀♀, 6♂♂; Osmanlı (91m)- Stream: 11.06.2014, 2♂♂; Keşan- Çeltik (140m)- Stream: 09.09.2013, 3♀♀, 7♂♂; Mecidiye (45m)- Stream: 09.09.2013, 3♀♀, 3♂♂; Sazlıdere (119m) - Stream: 09.09.2013, 1♀, 6♂♂; Lalapaşa- Çalidere (230m)- Stream: 15.07.2014, 1♂; Çömlekköy (94m)- Çoban Stream: 14.08.2013, 3♀♀, 5♂♂; Kalkansöğüt (415m)- Stream: 15.07.2014, 4♀♀, 8♂♂; Ömeroba (350m)- Süloğlu Stream: 01.09.2013, 13♀♀, 15♂♂; Süleymandanişment (384m)- Pond: 01.09.2013, 1♂; Merkez- Ahi (87m)- Stream: 22.08.2013, 5♀♀, 2♂♂; Hasanağa (60m)- Stream: 01.06.2014, 1♀, 3♂♂; İskender (87m) - Sazlı Stream: 15.03.2014, 5♀♀, 5♂♂; Süloğlu- Büyükgerdelli (163m)- Stream: 17.06.2013, 2♀♀, 1♂; Uzunköprü- Çöpköy (87m) - Stream: 30.08.2013, 2♀♀, 9♂♂; Çöpköy (87m) - Pond: 30.08.2013, 21♀♀, 1♂; Danişment (60m) - Koca Stream: 30.08.2013, 2♀♀; Kırkavak (80m)- Stream: 06.09.2013, 8♀♀, 11♂♂; Turnacı (90m) - Stream: 30.08.2013, 2♀♀, 6♂♂.

Gerris Fabricius, 1794***Gerris (Gerris) argentatus* Schummel, 1832**

Material examined: Enez- Abdurrahim (27m)- Stream: 12.09.2013, 1♀; Hisarlı (203m) - Pond: 23.06.2013, 2♀♀, 1♂; Karaincirli (32m)- Suvat Stream: 12.09.2013, 3♀♀, 2♂♂; Dalyan Lake (0m): 07.04.2014, 2♀♀, 3♂♂; Sultaniçe (36m)- Stream: 04.09.2013, 1♂; Havsa- Arpaç (119m)- Stream: 15.03.2014, 1♀; Bostanlı (88m)- Stream: 11.06.2014, 6♀♀, 4♂♂; Çukurköy (60m)- Stream: 03.06.2014, 9♀♀, 11♂♂; Osmanlı (91m)- Stream: 11.06.2014, 6♀♀, 2♂♂; Söğütlüdere (112m) - Seymen Stream: 20.08.2013, 1♀; Tahal (50m)- Stream: 13.06.2014, 2♂♂; Yolageldi (54m)- Trough: 11.06.2014, 9♀♀, 4♂♂; İpsala- Sarıcaali

23m)- Stream: 12.08.2014, 2♀♀; Sultan- köy (59m)- Dam evacuation: 12.09.2013, 1♂; Keşan- Beğendik (114m)- Pond: 23.08.2014, 2♀♀; Dişbudak (92m)- Stream: 09.09.2013, 1♂; Doğanca (92m)- Stream: 09.09.2013, 1♂; Lalapaşa- Çömlekköy (94m)- Çoban Stream: 14.08.2013, 1♂; Hamzabeyli (378m)- Pond: 15.07.2014, 8♀♀, 8♂♂; Taşlımüsel- lim (180m)- Stream: 21.09.2013, 1♂; Vaysal (438m)- Pond: 15.07.2014, 5♀♀, 4♂♂; Meriç- Büyükaltıağaç (40m)- Stream: 12.08.2014, 1♀; Nasuhbey (33m) - Pond: 04.08.2014, 2♀♀, 9♂♂; Olacak (60m)- Pond: 04.08.2014, 1♀, 3♂♂; Seren (40m)- Pond: 12.09.2013, 1♀; Subaşı (19m)- Pond: 12.08.2014, 1♀; Merkez- Avarız (42m) - Tunca River: 14.08.2013, 2♂♂; Balkan Yerleşkesi (41m) - Yurt ar- kası- Stream: 21.06.2013, 3♀♀; Bosnaköy (33m)- Rice field: 29.05.2014, 3♀♀, 2♂♂; Budakdoğanca (116m)- Pond: 15.09.2013, 1♀; Demirhanlı (114m)- Stream: 07.03.2014, 3♀♀, 7♂♂; Eskikadın (74m)- Pond: 15.09.2013, 2♀♀, 3♂♂; Ha- sanağa (60m)- Stream: 01.06.2014, 2♀♀, 1♂; İskender (87m) - Sazlı Stream: 15.03.2014, 1♀, 2♂♂; Kent Ormanı (41m)- Meriç River: 23.07.2013, 1♂; 1♀; Korucu (140m)- Pond: 01.06.2014, 4♀♀, 5♂♂; between Musabeyli- Demirhanlı (113m)- Pond: 07.03.2014, 10♀♀, 6♂♂; Merkez- Pazarkule (35m)- Meriç River: 23.07.2013, 1♀; Üyükütatar (44m)- Stream: 29.05.2014, 2♀♀, 4♂♂; Üyükütat- ar (44m)- Water channel: 29.05.2014, 1♀; Süloğlu- Büyükgerdelli (163m)- Stream: 17.06.2013, 1♀, 1♂; Büyükger- delli (163m)- Pond: 12.06.2013, 5♀♀, 6♂♂; Büyükgerdelli (163m)- Pool: 15.06.2013, 2♀♀, 3♂♂; Büyükgerdelli (163m)- Puddle: 13.03.2014, 5♀♀, 3♂♂; Stream (156m): 31.08.2013, 3♀♀, 2♂♂; Between Süloğlu- Küküler (160m)- Pond: 13.03.2014, 2♀♀, 2♂♂; Yağcılı (165)- Stream: 21.09.2013, 2♀♀; Between Uzunköprü- Bayramlı- Ye- niköy (80m) - Rice field: 30.08.2013, 5♀♀, 4♂♂; Bildır (80m)- Stream: 30.08.2013, 1♀; Değirmenci (49m)- Stream: 06.09.2013, 5♀♀, 1♂; Değirmenci (49m)- Pond: 06.09.2013, 1♀; Ergene River (32m): 30.08.2013, 2♀♀; Kırkavak (80m)- Stream: 06.09.2013, 1♀; Meşeli (88m)-

Stream: 13.06.2014, 2♀♀, 1♂.

***Gerris (Gerris) costae fieberi* Stichel, 1938**

Material examined: Havsa- Yolageldi (54m)- Trough: 11.06.2014, 5♀♀, 5♂♂; Lalapaşa- Hamzabeyli (378m)- Pond: 15.07.2014, 1♀; Kalkansöğüt (415m)- Stream: 15.07.2014, 2♀♀; Merkez- Balkan Yerleşkesi (41m) - Yurt arkası- Stream: 21.06.2013, 1♂; Hasanağa (60m)- Stream: 01.06.2014, 1♂; Korucu (140m)- Stream: 01.06.2014, 1♀; Meriç- Kavaklı (77m)- Stream: 01.06.2014, 2♀♀, 3♂♂; Uzunköprü- Bildır (80m)- Pond: 30.08.2013, 1♂.

***Gerris (Gerris) lacustris* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Material examined: Havsa- Arpaç (119m)- Stream: 15.03.2014, 1♀, 1♂; Bos- tanlı (88m)- Stream: 11.06.2014, 3♀♀; Çukurköy (60m)- Stream: 03.06.2014, 2♀♀; Osmanlı (91m)- Stream: 11.06.2014, 1♂; Şerbettar (83m)- Ova Stream: 03.06.2014, 2♀♀; İpsala- İbriktepe (127m) - Stream: 12.08.2014, 1♀; Turpçular (29m)- Stream: 23.08.2014, 1♂; Keşan- Dişbudak (92m)- Stream: 09.09.2013, 2♀♀, 6♂♂; Mecidiye (45m)- Stream: 26.08.2014, 1♀, 1♂; Mercan (38m)- irriga- tion channel: 09.09.2013, 1♂; Lalapaşa- Çalidere (230m)- Stream: 15.07.2014, 1♂; Çömlekköy (94m) - Çoban Stream: 14.08.2013, 2♀♀; Kalkansöğüt (415m)- Stream: 15.07.2014, 1♀; Ömeroba (350m) - Süloğlu Stream: 01.09.2013, 1♀, 3♂♂; Taşlımüselim (180m)- Stream: 21.09.2013, 8♀♀, 10♂♂; Meriç- Kavaklı (77m)- Stream: 01.06.2014, 2♀♀; Seren (40m)- Pond: 12.09.2013, 1♂; Merkez (41m)- Stream: 03.08.2013, 1♂; Ahi (87m) - Stream: 22.08.2013, 2♀♀, 1♂; Avarız (42m) - Tunca River: 14.08.2013, 4♀♀; Balkan Yerleşkesi (41m) - Yurt arkası- Stream: 21.06.2013, 2♂♂; Bosnaköy (33m)- Rice field: 29.05.2014, 1♀; Hasanağa (60m)- Stream: 01.06.2014, 1♀; Karabulut (123m)- Trough: 15.09.2013, 1♀, 2♂♂; Merkez-Pazarkule (35m)- Meriç River: 23.07.2013, 1♀; Uzgaç (163m)- Stream: 22.08.2013, 2♀♀, 1♂; Süloğlu- Büyükger- delli (163m)- Stream: 17.06.2013, 10♀♀,

6♂♂; Büyükgerdelli (163m)- Pool: 15.06.2013, 2♀♀; Stream (156m): 31.08.2013, 3♀♀, 7♂♂; Sülecik (208m)- Stream: 21.09.2013, 3♀♀, 3♂♂; Uzunköprü- Beykonağı (115m)- Stream: 31.08.2014, 1♀; Bildır (80m)- Stream: 30.08.2013, 8♀♀, 11♂♂; Çöpköy (87m)- Stream: 30.08.2013, 1♀; Hamidiye (108m)- Stream: 06.09.2013, 1♂; Kırkavak (80m)- Stream: 06.09.2013, 1♀, 1♂; Meşeli (88m)- Stream: 13.06.2014, 1♀, 3♂♂.

Gerris (Gerris) maculatus Tamanini, 1946

Material examined: Enez- Hisarlı (203m) - Pond: 23.06.2013, 1♀; Merkez- Korucu (140m)- Pond: 01.06.2014, 1♀; Süloğlu-Büyükgerdelli (163m)- Stream: 17.06.2013, 2♂♂.

Gerris (Gerris) thoracicus Schummel, 1832

Material examined: Enez- Hisarlı (203m) - Pond: 23.06.2013, 1♀, 2♂♂; Yenice (70m)- Trough: 24.08.2014, 1♀, 1♂; Havsa- Çukurköy (60m)- Stream: 03.06.2014, 1♂; Osmanlı (91m)- Stream: 11.06.2014, 1♂; Tahal (50m)- Stream: 13.06.2014, 5♀♀, 1♂; Keşan-KocaStream Dam evacuation: 09.09.2013, 1♂; Lalapaşa- Çömlekköy (94m) - Çoban Stream: 14.08.2013, 1♂; Hamzabeyli (378m)- Pond: 15.07.2014, 1♂; Kalkansöğüt (415m)- Stream: 15.07.2014, 1♂; Meriç- Kavaklı (77m)- Stream: 01.06.2014, 1♂; Merkez- Balkan Yerleşkesi (41m) - Yurt arkası- Stream: 21.06.2013, 2♂♂; Demirhanlı (114m)- Stream: 07.03.2014, 2♀♀, 4♂♂; Hasanağa (60m)- Stream: 01.06.2014, 1♀, 1♂; Orhaniye (15m) - Stream: 03.09.2013, 4♀♀, 3♂♂; Süloğlu- Büyükgerdelli (163m)- Puddle: 13.03.2014, 1♀, 1♂; Stream (156m): 31.08.2013, 1♀; Uzunköprü- Bildır (80m)- Stream: 30.08.2013, 1♂.

HYDROMETRIDAE Billberg, 1820

Hydrometra Latreille, 1796

Hydrometra stagnorum (Linnaeus, 1758)

Material examined: İpsala- İbriktepe (127m)- Stream: 12.08.2014, 1♀; Keşan- Çeltik (140m)- Stream: 09.09.2013, 3♀♀, 1♂; Çobançeşme (171m)- Dam evacuation: 23.08.2014, 1♀; Dişbudak (92m)- Stream: 09.09.2013, 3♀♀, 3♂♂; Mercan (38m)- Dam evacuation: 09.09.2013, 1♀, 1♂; Mercan (38m)- irrigation channel: 09.09.2013, 1♀, 2♂♂; Sazlıdere (119m)- Stream: 09.09.2013, 1♀; Lalapaşa- Çömlekköy (94m) - Çoban Stream: 14.08.2013, 7♀♀, 4♂♂; Kalkansöğüt (415m)- Stream: 15.07.2014, 1♂; Ömeroba (350m) - Süloğlu Stream: 01.09.2013, 1♂; Meriç- Kavaklı (77m)- Stream: 01.06.2014, 2♀♀, 1♂; Merkez- İskender (87m) - Sazlı Stream: 15.03.2014, 1♀; Korucu (140m)- Pond: 01.06.2014, 2♀♀; Merkez-Pazarkule (35m)- Meriç River: 23.07.2013, 1♀; Süloğlu (156m) - Stream: 31.08.2013, 5♀♀, 2♂♂; Uzunköprü- Beykonağı (115m)- Stream: 31.08.2014, 4♀♀, 2♂♂; Çöpköy (87m) - Stream: 30.08.2013, 2♀♀, 1♂; Kırkavak (80m)- Stream: 06.09.2013, 4♀♀, 2♂♂; Turnacı (90m)- Stream: 30.08.2013, 4♀♀, 5♂♂.

VELIIDAE Brullé, 1836

Microvelia Westwood, 1834

Microvelia (Picaultia) pygmaea (Dufour, 1833)

Material examined: Enez- Işıklı (27m)- Stream: 24.08.2014, 3♀♀, 1♂; Yenice (70m)- Trough: 24.08.2014, 14♀♀, 8♂♂; İpsala-Sarıcaali (23m)- Stream: 12.08.2014, 1♂; Turpçular (29m)- Stream: 23.08.2014, 1♀; Keşan- Kozköy (64m)- Stream: 23.08.2014, 6♀♀, 3♂♂; Pınar (174m)- Water channel: 26.08.2014, 3♂♂; Meriç- Seren (40m)- Pond: 12.09.2013, 1♀; Merkez- Balkan Yerleşkesi (41m)- Stream: 19.09.2014, 1♂; Balkan Yerleşkesi (41m) - Yurt arkası- Stream: 21.06.2013, 3♀, 2♂♂; İskender (87m) - Sazlı Stream: 15.03.2014, 2♀♀.

Velia Latreille, 1804

***Velia (Plesiovelia) affinis filippii*
Tamanini, 1947**

Material examined: Havsa-Bostanlı (88m)- Stream: 11.06.2014, 6♀♀, 5♂♂, 1 nimf; Osmanlı (91m)- Stream: 11.06.2014, 2♀♀; Merkez- Balkan Yerleşkesi (41m) - Stream: 10.06.2013, 21♀♀, 8 ♂♂, 18 nimf; Hasanağa (60m)- Stream: 01.06.2014, 2♀♀, 3♂♂.

NEPOMORPHA Popov, 1968

BELOSTOMATIDAE Leach, 1815

***Lethocerus* Mayr, 1853**

***Lethocerus (Lethocerus) patruelis*
(Stål, 1854)**

Material examined: İpsala- Koyuntepe (28m) - Telmata- Lake: 03.09.2013, 1♀, 2 nimf; Tevfikiye (11m)- irrigation channel: 12.09.2013, 1♀; Meriç- Karayusuflu (24m)- Pond: 12.09.2013, 2♀♀, 2♂♂; Koca Stream (40m): 12.09.2013, 1♀; Merkez (41m)- Roadside: 08.09.2013, 1♀; Uzunköprü- Değirmenci (49m)- Pond: 06.09.2013, 4♀♀; Bayramlı- Yeniköy arası (80m) - Water channel: 30.08.2013, 5♀♀, 3♂♂, 3 nimf.

CORIXIDAE Leach, 1815

***Corixa* Geoffroy, 1762**

***Corixa affinis* Leach, 1817**

Material examined: Enez- Abdurrahim (27m)- Trough: 12.09.2013, 2♀♀, 2♂♂; Hisarlı (203m) - Pond: 23.06.2013, 1♀, 6♂♂; Vakıf (28m)- Stream: 12.09.2013, 6♀♀, 2♂♂; Yenimahalle (30m)- Pond: 12.09.2013, 8♀♀, 4♂♂; Havsa- Yolageldi (54m)- Trough: 11.06.2014, 1♂; İpsala-Turpçular (29m)- Stream: 23.08.2014, 1♀, 5♂♂; Yenikarpuzlu (20m)- Water channel: 12.09.2013, 1♀; Keşan- Beğendik (114m)- Pond: 23.08.2014, 1♀; Lalacık (158m)- Trough: 23.08.2014, 1♀; Mecidiye (45m)- Stream: 09.09.2013, 16♀♀, 11♂♂; Mercan (38m)- irrigation channel: 09.09.2013, 2♀♀, 1♂; Sazlıdere (119m) - Trough: 09.09.2013, 5♀♀, 4♂♂; Yerlisu (174m)- Water channel: 09.09.2013, 1♂; Lalapaşa-Çömlekköy (94m)- Çoban Stream: 14.08.2013, 41♀♀, 22♂♂; Ömeroba (350m)- Süloğlu Stream: 01.09.2013,

1♂; Süleymandanişment (384m)- Pond: 01.09.2013, 1♀, 1♂; Vaysal (438m)- Pond: 15.07.2014, 1♂; Meriç- Yenicegörece (20m)- Trough:12.09.2013, 1♀, 1♂; Merkez- Ahi (87m) - Stream: 22.08.2013, 2♀♀, 2♂♂; Budakdoğanca (116m)- Pond: 15.09.2013, 1♂; Balkan Yerleşkesi (41m)- Stream: 21.06.2013, 1♂; Hacrumur (136m)- Pond: 13.03.2014, 2♂♂; İskender (87m)- Sazlı Stream: 20.08.2013, 1♀, 1♂; Orhaniye (15m) - Stream: 03.09.2013, 2♀♀; Süloğlu- Büyükgerdelli (163m)- Stream: 17.06.2013, 3♀♀, 2♂♂; Büyükgerdelli (163m)- Puddle: 13.03.2014, 3♀♀, 2♂♂; Domurcalı (199m)- Trough: 21.09.2013, 1♂; Geçkinli (151m)- Stream (144m):01.09.2013, 1♂; Between Süloğlu- Lalapaşa (160m)- Pond: 01.09.2013, 9♀♀, 5♂♂; Tatarlar (236m)- Trough: 21.09.2013, 4♀♀; Uzunköprü- Bildır (80m)- Stream: 30.08.2013, 1♂; Çalıköy (97m)- Pond: 12.09.2013, 3♀♀, 2♂♂; Kavacık (52m)- Pond: 06.09.2013, 12♀♀, 8♂♂.

***Corixa punctata* (Illiger, 1807)**

Material examined: Enez- Yenimahalle (30m)- Pond: 12.09.2013, 2♀♀; İpsala-Yenikarpuzlu (20m)- Water channel: 12.09.2013, 1♀; Lalapaşa- Çömlekköy (94m) - Çoban Stream: 14.08.2013, 21♀♀, 15♂♂; Ömeroba (350m)- Süloğlu Stream: 01.09.2013, 1♀; Süleymandanişment (384m) - Pond: 01.09.2013, 1♀, 11♂♂; Merkez- Balkan Yerleşkesi (41m) - Stream: 21.06.2013, 1♀; Budakdoğanca (116m)- Pond: 15.09.2013, 8♀♀, 5♂♂; İskender (87m)- Sazlı Stream: 20.08.2013, 1♂; Süloğlu- Büyükgerdelli (163m)- Puddle: 13.03.2014, 2♀♀; Stream (156m): 31.08.2013, 1♂; Between Süloğlu- Lalapaşa (160m)- Pond: 01.09.2013, 9♀♀, 6♂♂; Uzunköprü- Çalıköy (97m)- Pond: 12.09.2013, 2♂♂; Kavacık (52m)- Pond: 06.09.2013, 1♀; Süloğlu- Sülecik (208m)- Stream: 21.09.2013, 1♀; Tatarlar (236m)- Trough: 21.09.2013, 1♀, 5♂♂.

***Micronecta* Kirkaldy, 1897**

***Micronecta (Dichaetonecta) scholtzi*
(Fieber, 1860)**

Material examined: Enez- Büyük Gala

Lake (0m): 07.04.2014, 5♀♀, 10♂♂; Işıklı (27m)- Stream: 24.08.2014, 1♀, 1♂; Sultanice (36m)- Stream: 04.09.2013, 41♀♀, 79♂♂; Yenimahalle (30m)- Pond: 12.09.2013, 2♀♀, 4♂♂; Havsa- Söğütlüdere (112m) - Seymen Stream: 20.08.2013, 3♀♀, 5♂♂; İpsala- Turpçular (29m)- Stream: 23.08.2014, 6♂♂; Yenikarpuzlu (20m)- Water channel: 12.09.2013, 1♀; Keşan- Beğendik (114m)- Pond: 23.08.2014, 1♂; Kozköy (64m)- Stream: 23.08.2014, 1♀, 1♂; Mercan- Dam evacuation: 09.09.2013, 1♀; Mercan (38m)- irrigation channel: 09.09.2013, 2♀♀, 10♂♂; Pınar (174m)- Water channel: 26.08.2014, 4♀♀, 3♂♂; Lalapaşa- Ömeroba (350m)- Süloğlu Stream: 01.09.2013, 21♀♀, 7♂♂; Vaysal (438m)- Pond: 15.07.2014, 27♀♀, 53♂♂, 49 nimf; Meriç-Büyükaltıağaç (40m)- Stream: 12.08.2014, 1♀, 1♂; Koca Stream (40m): 12.09.2013, 2♀♀; Seren (40m)- Pond: 12.09.2013, 6♂♂; Merkez- Eskikadın (74m)- Pond: 15.09.2013, 5♀♀, 6♂♂; Süloğlu- Sülecik (208m)- Stream: 21.09.2013, 1♂; Uzunköprü- Degirmenci (49m)- Pond: 06.09.2013, 3♀♀; Dereköy (57m)- Stream: 31.08.2014, 3♀♀, 3♂♂; Kavacık (52m)- Pond: 06.09.2013, 4♀♀, 8♂♂, 2 nimf; Kırkavak (80m)- Stream: 06.09.2013, 1♀, 1♂; Türkobası (26m)- Ana Stream: 06.09.2013, 1♀.

Sigara Fabricius, 1775

Sigara (Pseudovermicorixa) nigro-lineata nigrolineata (Fieber, 1848)

Material examined: Enez- Abdurrahim (27m)- Trough: 12.09.2013, 2♀♀, 1♂; Gülçavuş (18m)- Trough: 04.09.2013, 20♀♀, 9♂♂; Işıklı (27m)- Stream: 24.08.2014, 1♀, 1♂; Trough (24m): 12.09.2013, 4♂♂; Yenice (70m)- Trough: 24.08.2014, 9♀♀, 19♂♂; Havsa- Azatlı (100m)- Trough: 29.05.2014, 8♀♀, 12♂♂; Bostanlı (88m)- Stream: 11.06.2014, 3♀♀, 1♂; Çukurköy (60m)- Stream: 03.06.2014, 1♀; Osmanlı (91m)- Stream: 11.06.2014, 2♀♀; Osmanlı (91m)- Trough: 11.06.2014, 6♀♀, 3♂♂; Söğütlüdere (112m)- Seymen Stream; 20.08.2013, 3♀♀, 1♂; Tahal (50m)- Stream: 13.06.2014, 1♂; Yolageldi (54m)- Trough: 11.06.2014, 9♀♀, 7♂♂; İpsala- Balabancık (36m)- Trough: 12.09.2013, 4♀♀, 3♂♂; Korucu (75m)- Stream: 23.08.2014, 1♀, 1♂; Sarıcaali (23m)- Stream: 12.08.2014, 9♀♀, 9♂♂; Sultanköy (59m)- Trough: 12.09.2013, 3♀♀, 1♂; Turpçular (29m)- Stream: 23.08.2014, 1♀; Keşan- Boztepe (48m)- Trough: 26.05.2014, 16♀♀, 6♂♂; Kozköy (64m)- Stream: 23.08.2014, 7♀♀, 8♂♂; Küçükdoğanca (46m) - Manav Fountain: 03.09.2013, 20♀♀, 17♂♂; Lalacık (158m)- Trough: 23.08.2014, 16♀♀, 20♂♂; Mecidiye (45m)- Stream: 09.09.2013, 1♀, 1♂; Mecidiye (45m)- Stream: 26.08.2014, 1♀; Mercan (38m)- irrigation channel: 09.09.2013, 7♀♀, 3♂♂; Pınar (174m)- Water channel: 26.08.2014, 2♂♂; Yaylaköy (154m)- Puddle: 26.08.2014, 5♀♀, 5♂♂; Lalapaşa- Çömlekköy (94m)- Çoban Stream: 14.08.2013, 6♀♀; Hacıdanışment (438m)- Trough: 01.09.2013, 5♀♀, 7♂♂; Hamzabeyli (378m)- Pond: 15.07.2014, 1♂; Kalkansöğüt (415m)- Stream: 15.07.2014, 1♀, 1♂; Ömeroba (350m)- Süloğlu Stream: 01.09.2013, 2♀♀, 4♂♂; Sarıdanışment (285m)- Stream: 21.09.2013, 5♀♀, 1♂; Meriç- Akçadam (60m)- Trough: 12.09.2013, 1♀; Kavaklı (77m)- Stream: 01.06.2014, 3♀♀, 4♂♂; Kavaklı (77m)- Trough: 04.08.2014, 12♀♀, 4♂♂; Nasuhbey (33m)- Pond: 04.08.2014, 1♀; Yenicegörece (20m)- Trough: 12.09.2013, 1♀; Merkez- Ahi (87m) - Stream: 22.08.2013, 5♀♀, 2♂♂; Demirhanlı (114m)- Stream: 07.03.2014, 2♀♀; Ekmekçi (147m)- Stream: 15.09.2013, 1♀; Hacıumur (136m)- Pond: 13.03.2014, 3♀♀, 4♂♂; Hacıumur (136m)- Trough: 07.03.2014, 3♀♀, 1♂; İskender (87m)- Sazlı Stream: 15.03.2014, 1♀, 4♂♂; Karabulut (123m)- Trough: 15.09.2013, 3♀♀, 2♂♂; Kemal (84m)- Trough: 15.09.2013, 1♀; Orhaniye (15m) - Trough: 03.09.2013, 33♀♀, 31♂♂; Uzgaç (163m)- Stream: 22.08.2013, 3♀♀; Süloğlu- Büyükgerdelli (163m)- Puddle: 13.03.2014, 9♀♀, 7♂♂; Süloğlu- Çeşmeköy arası (200m)- Trough: 13.06.2014, 15♀♀; Domurcalı (199m)- Trough: 21.09.2013, 11♀♀, 9♂♂; Geçkinli (151m)- Stream: 01.09.2013, 2♀♀, 1♂; Tatarlar (236m)- Trough: 21.09.2013, 3♀♀, 3♂♂; Uzunköprü- Balaban (26m)- Trough: 12.08.2014, 1♀, 1♂; Bayramlı- Yeniköy

arası (80m)- water channel: 30.08.2013, 6♀♀, 9♂♂; Çiftlikköy (12m)- Stream: 04.08.2014, 11♀♀, 10♂♂; Danişment (60m) - Koca Stream: 30.08.2013, 34♀♀, 18♂♂; Dereköy (57m)- Stream: 31.08.2014, 6♀♀, 2♂♂; Elmalı (120m)- Trough: 31.08.2014, 2♀♀, 2♂♂; Ergene River (32m): 30.08.2013, 13♀♀, 7♂♂; Eskiköy (72m)- Puddle: 13.06.2014, 1♀, 1♂; Hamidiye (108m)- Stream: 06.09.2013, 2♀♀, 2♂♂; Harmanlı (180m)- Trough: 31.08.2014, 6♀♀, 11♂♂; Kadiağılı (139m)- Fountain: 06.09.2013, 24♀♀, 11♂♂; Kavacık (52m)- Trough: 06.09.2013, 9♀♀, 4♂; Meşeli (88m)- Stream: 13.06.2014, 1♂; Saçlımüsellim (28m)- Trough: 13.06.2014, 21♀♀, 6♂♂; Süleymaniye (281m)- Trough: 31.08.2014, 1♀, 3♂♂; Turnacı (90m) - Stream: 30.08.2013, 1♀, 1♂; Türkobası (26m)- Ana Stream: 06.09.2013, 1♀.

***Sigara (Retrocorixa) limitata limitata* (Fieber, 1848)**

Material examined: Havsa- Söğütlüdere (112m) - Seymen Stream: 20.08.2013, 2♂♂; Merkez- Budakdoğanca (116m)- Pond: 15.09.2013, 1♀; İskender (87m)- Sazlı Stream: 20.08.2013, 1♀; Karabulut (123m)- Trough: 15.09.2013, 1♂; Kemal (84m)- Trough: 15.09.2013, 2♀♀, 1♂; Uzgaç (163m)- Stream: 22.08.2013, 1♂; Süloğlu- Geçkinli (151m)- Stream: 01.09.2013, 1♀; Sülecik (208m)- Stream: 21.09.2013, 1♀, 1♂; Tatarlar (236m)- Trough: 21.09.2013, 1♀, 1♂; Yağcılı (165)- Stream: 21.09.2013, 2♀♀, 1♂; Between Uzunköprü - Bayramlı- Yeniköy (80m)- water channel: 30.08.2013, 1♀, 1♂; Bildir (80m)- Stream: 30.08.2013, 1♂; Çalıköy (97m)- Pond: 12.09.2013, 1♂; Hamidiye (108m)- Stream: 06.09.2013, 1♀; Kavacık (52m)- Pond: 06.09.2013, 3♂♂.

***Sigara (Sigara) striata* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Material examined: Havsa- Tahal (50m)- Stream: 13.06.2014, 2♀♀, 2♂♂; Keşan-Mercan (38m)- irrigation channel: 09.09.2013, 1♂; Meriç- Büyükaltağaç (40m)- Stream: 12.08.2014, 3♀♀, 3♂♂; Subaşı (19m)- Pond: 12.08.2014, 1♀, 1♂; Uzunköprü- Dereköy (57m)- Stream: 31.08.2014, 3♂♂.

***Sigara (Subsigara) iactans* Jansson, 1983**

Material examined: Enez- Sultaniçe (36m)- Stream: 04.09.2013, 1♀, 1♂; Havsa- Bostanlı (88m)- Stream: 11.06.2014, 1♂; Lalapaşa- Hamzabeyli (378m)- Pond: 15.07.2014, 14♀♀, 2♂♂; Vaysal (438m)- Pond: 15.07.2014, 8♀♀, 7♂♂; between Merkez- Musabeyli- Demirhanlı (113m)- Pond: 07.03.2014, 1♀; Süloğlu- Yağcılı (165)- Stream: 21.09.2013, 5♀♀, 1♂; Uzunköprü- Çalıköy (97m)- Pond: 12.09.2013, 1♀.

***Sigara (Vermicorixa) lateralis* (Leach, 1817)**

Material examined: Enez - Abdurrahim (27m)- Trough: 12.09.2013, 4♀♀, 1♂; Hisarlı (203m) - Pond: 23.06.2013, 32♀♀, 10♂♂; Hisarlı (203m)- Pond: 04.09.2013, 10♀♀, 14♂♂; Sultaniçe (36m)- Stream: 04.09.2013, 4♂♂; Vakıf (28m)- Stream: 12.09.2013, 1♀, 1♂; Trough (24m): 12.09.2013, 1♀, 1♂; Yenice (70m)- Trough: 24.08.2014, 1♀, 1♂; Yenimahalle (30m)- Pond: 12.09.2013, 9♀♀, 5♂♂; Havsa- Abalar (70m)- Stream: 30.08.2014, 37♀♀, 26♂♂; Bostanlı (88m)- Stream: 11.06.2014, 1♀; Oğulpaşa (85m)- Stream: 30.08.2014, 49♀♀, 17♂♂; Söğütlüdere (112m) - Seymen Stream: 20.08.2013, 2♀♀, 4♂♂; Tahal (50m)- Stream: 13.06.2014, 15♀♀, 8♂♂; Yolageldi (54m)- Trough: 11.06.2014, 1♂; İpsala- Balabancık (36m)- Stream: 12.09.2013, 29♀♀, 5♂♂; Balabancık (36m)- Trough: 12.09.2013, 4♂♂; DSİ(20m) - Water channel: 12.09.2013, 4♀♀, 8♂♂; Korucu (75m)- Stream: 23.08.2014, 1♀, 7♂♂; Sultanköy (59m)- Trough: 12.09.2013, 10♀♀, 6♂♂; Turpçular (29m)- Stream: 23.08.2014, 10♀♀, 12♂♂; Yenikarpuzlu (20m)- Water channel: 01.09.2013, 9♀♀, 7♂♂; Keşan- Beğendik (114m)- Pond: 23.08.2014, 6♀♀, 4♂♂; Boztepe (48m)- Trough: 26.05.2014, 1♂; Lalacık (158m)- Trough: 23.08.2014, 4♀♀, 3♂♂; Mecidiye (45m)- Stream: 26.08.2014, 1♂; Sazlıdere (119m)- Trough: 09.09.2013, 1♀; Yaylaköy (154m)- Puddle: 26.08.2014, 13♀♀, 5♂♂; Yerlisu (174m) - Water channel: 09.09.2013, 4♀♀, 1♂; Lalapaşa- Çömlekköy (94m)- Çoban

Stream: 14.08.2013, 2♀♀, 2♂♂; Hacıda-
nişment (438m)- Trough: 01.09.2013,
2♀♀, 1♂; Hamzabeyli (378m)- Pond:
15.07.2014, 1♂; Pond (166m): 01.09.
2013, 10♀♀, 9♂♂; Süleymandanişment
(384m) - Pond: 01.09.2013, 27♀♀, 12♂♂;
Meriç- Adasarhanlı (38m)- Pond: 12.08.
2014, 16♀♀, 21♂♂; Büyükalıtiyağaç (40m)-
Stream: 12.08.2014, 2♀♀, 3♂♂; Nasuhbey
(33m)- Pond: 04.08.2014, 7♀♀, 1♂; Seren
(40m)- Pond: 12.09.2013, 10♀♀, 18♂♂;
Yenicegörece (20m)- Trough: 12.09.2013,
40♀♀, 23♂♂; Merkez- Hacıumur (136m)-
Pond: 13.03.2014, 7♀♀, 8♂♂; Demirhanlı
(114m)- Stream: 07.03.2014, 2♀♀, 2♂♂;
İskender (87m)- Sazlı Stream: 20.08.
2013, 3♀♀; between Musabeyli- Demir-
hanlı (113m)- Pond: 07.03.2014, 1♀; Mu-
sabeyli (113m)- Pool: 07.03.2014, 1♀; Ke-
mal (84m)- Trough: 15.09.2013, 2♀, 3♂♂;
Orhaniye (15m)- Stream: 03.09.2013,
39♀♀, 27♂♂; Orhaniye (15m)- Trough:
03.09.2013, 2♀♀, 1♂; Süloğlu- Büyükger-
delli (163m)- Çamlık- Puddle: 13.03.
2014, 1♀; Stream (156m): 31.08.2013,
1♀; Domurcalı (199m)- Trough: 21.09.
2013, 3♀♀; Geçkinli (151m)- Stream:
01.09.2013, 11♀♀, 20♂♂; Kerametlin
(200m)- Pond: 12.06.2014, 7♀♀, 5♂♂;
Between Süloğlu- Lalapaşa (160m)-
Pond: 01.09.2013, 70♀♀, 51♂♂; Tatarlar
(236m)- Trough: 21.09.2013, 8♀♀, 1♂;
Uzunköprü- Alıç (114m)- Alıç Stream:
06.09.2013, 15♀♀, 5♂♂; Bayramlı- Yeni-
köy arası (80m) - Rice field: 30.08.2013,
5♀♀, 6♂♂; Beykonağı (115m)- Stream:
31.08.2014, 1♀; Bildır (80m) - Pond:
30.08.2013, 49♀♀, 35♂♂; Çalıköy (97m)-
Pond: 12.09.2013, 13♀♀, 15♂♂; Daniş-
ment (60m) - Koca Stream: 30.08.2013,
2♀♀, 2♂♂; Değirmenci (49m)- Pond:
06.09.2013, 3♀♀, 4♂♂; Dereköy (57m)-
Stream: 31.08.2014, 1♀, 3♂♂; Ergene Ri-
ver (32m): 30.08.2013, 2♂♂; Eskiköy
(72m)- Puddle: 13.06.2014, 7♀♀; Hamidi-
ye (108m)- Stream: 06.09.2013, 12♀♀,
13♂♂; Kadiyağılı (139m)- Fountain:
06.09.2013, 1♀, 2♂♂; Kavacık (52m)-
Pond: 06.09.2013, 28♀♀, 24♂♂; Türkobası
(26m)- Ana Stream: 06.09.2013, 13♀♀,
4♂♂.

NAUCORIDAE Leach, 1815

Ilyocoris Stål, 1861

Ilyocoris cimicoides cimicoides (Linnaeus, 1758)

Material examined: Lalapaşa- Hamza-
beyli (378m)- Pond: 15.07.2014, 2 nimf;
Pond (166m): 01.09.2013, 1♂; Merkez-
Üyükütatar (44m)- Stream: 29.05.2014,
1 nimf; Süloğlu- Büyükgerdelli (163m)-
Pond: 12.06.2013, 9 nimf.

NEPIDAE Latreille, 1802

Nepa Linnaeus, 1758

Nepa cinerea Linnaeus, 1758

Material examined: Havsa- Çukurköy
(60m)- Stream: 03.06.2014, 1 nimf; Os-
manlı (91m)- Stream: 11.06.2014, 2 nimf;
Söğütlüdere (112m)- Seymen Stream:
20.08.2013, 1♀; İpsala- İbriktepe (127m)-
Stream: 12.08.2014, 1♀; Keşan- Dişbu-
dak (92m)- Stream: 09.09.2013, 1 nimf;
Merkez- Ahi (87m) - Stream: 2♀♀; Balkan
Yerleşkesi (41m)- Stream: 10.06.2013, 1
nimf; Demirhanlı (114m)- Stream: 07.03.
2014, 1♀; Hasanağa (60m)- Stream:
01.06.2014, 1♀, 1♂; İskender (87m)- Sazlı
Stream: 20.08.2013, 1♂, 3nimf; Süloğlu
(156m)- Stream: 31.08.2013, 4nimf; Sü-
lecik (208m)- Stream: 21.09.2013, 1♀;
Uzunköprü- Meşeli (88m)- Stream:
13.06.2014, 2 nimf; Turnacı (90m) -
Stream: 30.08.2013, 1 nimf.

Ranatra Fabricius, 1790

Ranatra (Ranatra) linearis (Linnaeus, 1758)

Material examined: Lalapaşa- Hamza-
beyli (378m)- Pond: 15.07.2014, 1 nimf;
Meriç- Subaşı (19m)- Pond: 12.08.2014,
2 nimf; Merkez- Üyükütatar (44m)-
Water channel: 29.05.2014, 1♀.

NOTONECTIDAE Latreille, 1802

Notonecta Linnaeus, 1758

Notonecta (Notonecta) glauca glauca Linnaeus, 1758

Material examined: Havsa- Osmanlı
(91m)- Stream: 11.06.2014, 1♂; İpsala-

Sarıcaali (23m)- Stream: 12.08.2014, 1♀; Lalapaşa- Çalidere (230m)- Stream: 15.07.2014, 1♂; Merkez- Ahi (87m)- Stream: 22.08.2013, 6♀♀, 4♂♂; Balkan Yerleşkesi (41m) - Stream: 21.06.2013, 8♀♀, 2♂♂; Süloğlu- Büyükgerdelli (163m)- Pool: 15.06.2013, 2♂♂; Büyükgerdelli (163m)- Pond: 12.06.2013, 1♂; Uzunköprü- Bildır (80m)- Stream: 30.08.2013, 2♀♀.

Notonecta (Notonecta) maculata

Fabricius, 1794

Material examined: İpsala- Balabancık (36m)- Stream: 12.09.2013, 2♀♀, 3♂♂; Korucu (75m)- Stream: 23.08.2014, 4♀♀, 3♂♂; Keşan- Boztepe (48m)- Trough: 26.05.2014, 2♂♂; Çeltik (140m)- Stream: 09.09.2013, 3♀♀, 3♂♂; Dişbudak (92m)- Stream: 09.09.2013, 1♂; Mecidiye (45m)- Stream: 09.09.2013, 1♂; Mecidiye (45m)- Stream: 26.08.2014, 1♀; Mercan (38m)- irrigation channel (72m): 09.09.2013, 1♂; Pınar (174m)- Water channel: 26.08.2014, 1♂; Sazlıdere (119m) - Trough: 09.09.2013, 12♀♀; Lalapaşa- Çalidere (230m)- Stream: 15.07.2014, 1♀; Çömlekköy (94m) - Çoban Stream: 14.08.2013, 35♀♀, 27♂♂; Hacıdanışment (438m)- Trough: 01.09.2013, 1♀, 1♂; Lalapaşa- Kalkansöğüt (415m)- Stream: 15.07.2014, 5♀♀, 3♂♂; Ömeroba (350m)- Süloğlu Stream: 01.09.2013, 2♀♀, 1♂; Sarıdanışment (285m)- Stream: 21.09.2013, 7♀♀, 5♂♂; Taşlımüsellim (180m)- Stream: 21.09.2013, 1♀; Merkez- Ahi (87m)- Stream: 22.08.2013, 5♀♀, 5♂♂; Ekmekçi (147m)- Stream: 15.09.2013, 1♀, 1♂; Kemal (84m)- Stream: 15.09.2013, 1♀, 4♂♂; Kemal (84m)- Trough: 15.09.2013, 11♀♀, 2♂♂; Uzgaç (163m) - Stream: 22.08.2013, 13♀♀, 9♂♂; Süloğlu (156m) - Stream: 31.08.2013, 1♀; Domurcalı (199m)- Trough: 21.09.2013, 1♀; Uzunköprü- Balaban (26m)- Trough: 12.08.2014, 1♀, 1♂; Beykonağı (115m)- Stream: 31.08.2014, 1♂; Bildır (80m)- Stream: 30.08.2013, 1♂; Çöpköy (87m) - Stream: 30.08.2013, 1♀, 1♂; Harmanlı (180m)- Trough: 31.08.2014, 1♀; Kavacık (52m)- Trough: 06.09.2013, 2♀♀, 6♂♂; Meşeli (88m)- Stream: 13.06.2014, 1♂.

Notonecta (Notonecta) meridionalis **Poisson, 1926**

Material examined: Havsa- Yolageldi (54m)- Trough: 11.06.2014, 1♂; Lalapaşa - Çömlekköy (94m) - Çoban Stream: 14.08.2013, 2♂♂; Sarıdanışment (285m)- Stream: 21.09.2013, 1♂; Taşlımüsellim (180m)- Stream: 21.09.2013, 1♂; Merkez- Balkan Yerleşkesi (41m) - Stream: 10.06.2013, 1♂; Süloğlu- Büyükgerdelli (163m)- Stream: 17.06.2013, 1♂; Büyükgerdelli (163m)- Pool: 15.06.2013, 3♂♂.

Notonecta (Notonecta) obliqua **Thunberg, 1787**

Material examined: Havsa- Yolageldi (54m)- Trough: 11.06.2014, 2♂♂; Süloğlu - Büyükgerdelli (163m)- Pool: 15.06.2013, 1♂.

Notonecta (Notonecta) viridis Delcourt, **1909**

Material examined: Enez- Abdurrahim (27m)- Stream: 12.09.2013, 1♀, 1♂; Abdurrahim (27m)- Trough: 12.09.2013, 1♀, 1♂; Hisarlı (203m) - Pond: 23.06.2013, 6♀♀, 5♂♂; Yenimahalle (30m)- Pond: 12.09.2013, 1♀; Havsa- Söğütlüdere (112m)- Seymen Stream: 20.08.2013, 1♀; İpsala- Balabancık (36m)- Stream: 12.09.2013, 1♂; Keşan- Çeltik (140m)- Stream: 09.09.2013, 3♀♀, Dişbudak (92m)- Stream: 09.09.2013, 1♀, 2♂♂; Mecidiye (45m)- Stream: 09.09.2013, 4♀♀, 7♂♂; Sazlıdere (119m) - Trough: 09.09.2013, 2♀♀; Lalapaşa- Çalidere (230m)- Stream: 15.07.2014, 2♀♀, 6♂♂; Çömlekköy (94m) - Çoban Stream: 14.08.2013, 10♀♀, 5♂♂; Kalkansöğüt (415m)- Stream: 15.07.2014, 1♂; Ömeroba (350m)- Süloğlu Stream: 01.09.2013, 1♀, 3♂♂; Merkez- Ahi (87m) - Stream: 22.08.2013, 5♀♀, 6♂♂; Balkan Yerleşkesi (41m) - Stream: 21.06.2013, 5♀♀, 4♂♂; Budakdoğanca (116m)- Pond: 15.09.2013, 3♀♀, 4♂♂; Demirhanlı (114m)- Stream: 07.03.2014, 1♀, 1♂; Karabulut (123m)- Trough: 15.09.2013, 3♀♀, 9♂♂; Kemal (84m)- Trough: 15.09.2013, 1♀; between Musabeyli- Demirhanlı (113m)- Pond: 07.03.2014, 2♀♀, 6♂♂; Uzgaç (163m)- Stream: 22.08.2013, 18♀♀, 13♂♂; Süloğlu- Büyükgerdelli

(163m)- Stream: 17.06.2013, 2♀♀; Dörmürcalı (199m)- Trough: 21.09.2013, 1♀; Uzunköprü- Bildır (80m)- Stream: 30.08.2013, 3♀♀, 4♂♂; Çalıköy (97m)- Pond: 12.09.2013, 1♀.

PLEIDAE Fieber, 1851

Plea Leach, 1817

Plea minutissima minutissima Leach, 1817

Material examined: Lalapaşa- Hamzabeyli (378m)- Pond: 15.07.2014, 1♀; Vaysal (438m)- Pond: 15.07.2014, 1♀, 5♂♂; Meriç- Nasuhbey (33m)- Pond: 04.08.2014, 1 nimf; Merkez- Üyüklütatar (44m) - Stream: 29.05.2014, 1♀, 2♂♂; Between Süloğlu- Lalapaşa (160m)- Pond: 01.09.2014, 1♂.

DISCUSSION

As a result of a two-year study conducted in 129 locations with all kinds of wetlands, 14 species and 28 species belonging to 9 families from Gerromorpha and Nepomorpha were identified in the research area. The distribution of the determined species by families are as follows: Gerromorpha: 7 species and 2 genere belong to Gerridae, 1 species and 1 genus belong to Hydrometridae, 2 species and 2 genere belong to Veliidae; Nepomorpha: 1 species and 1 genus belong to Belastomatidae, 8 species and 3 genere belong to Corixidae, 1 species and 1 genus belong to Naucoridae, 2 species and 2 genere belong to Nepidae, 5 species and 1 genus belong to Notonectidae and 1 species 1 genus belong to Pleidae.

Among the species determined during research, *Aquarius ventralis*, *Gerris (Gerris) argentatus*, *Gerris (Gerris) costae fieberi*, *Gerris (Gerris) lacustris*, *Ilyocoris cimicoides cimicoides*, *Notonecta (Notonecta) glauca glauca*, *Notonecta (Notonecta) maculata*, *Notonecta (Notonecta) meridionalis*, *Notonecta (Notonecta) obliqua*, *Velia (Plesiovelia) affinis filippii* were also recorded for the first time from Edirne Province.

Microvelia are represented with two subgenus (*Microvelia* and *Picaultia*) and three species

(*Microvelia hozari*, *Microvelia pygmaea* and *Microvelia reticulata*) in Turkey. Of these species, *M. pygmaea* has been recorded before from several places in Anatolia as well as from Edirne in the Thrace Region (Önder *et al.*, 1984). In this study, this species has been identified in 10 different locations in Edirne Province.

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